

ASSESSING THE ECONOMIC EFFICIENCY OF FISH CAUGHT FROM THE AIDAR ARNASAY LAKES SYSTEM

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Abstract. *Increasing the volume of fishing from natural water bodies is an important factor in ensuring ecological stability and rational use of natural resources. Overfishing can lead to a decline in fish populations, which in turn disrupts biological balance and harms the fishing industry in the long term. Therefore, introducing modern technologies, applying scientifically-based fishing methods, and adhering to international ecological standards are essential steps to effectively organize this process. This is why the study was conducted in the largest natural water body in our country, the Aydar-Arnasoy Lakes System. The research was carried out from 2019 to 2022 in three reservoirs of the Aydar-Arnasoy Lakes System: Tuzkon and Aydarkul Lakes, and Arnasoy Reservoir. The economic evaluation of fish caught from various locations in these reservoirs was conducted.*

Keywords: *fishing industry, AALS, Economic efficiency, Profitability, pikeperch, fishing brigades, Shore price, Fishing, Commercial pikeperch, Income, Expense, crusian carp, common carp, roach fish.*

Introduction

The fishing industry plays a crucial role in ensuring food security, improving living standards, and maintaining ecological sustainability worldwide. This sector not only supplies high-quality fish products to local consumers but has also become one of the key branches of the economy by increasing export potential. The growing demand of the population and global climate change have made the intensive development of fishing an urgent issue. Furthermore, the implementation of advanced methods in fish farming (aquaculture) and fishing, the application of innovative technologies, and the maintenance of ecological balance are essential for ensuring the sustainable development of the fishing industry. This process, on one hand, requires the rational use of natural resources, and on the other hand, provides opportunities to create new jobs and stimulate the local economy through increased production[2].

Moreover, establishing effective collaboration between the public and private sectors, widely applying scientific research developments, and adhering to ecological standards are crucial for the development of the fishing industry. These factors help shape the fishing industry as a sector that contributes not only to economic growth but also to ecological and social stability. Increasing the volume of fish caught is currently one of the urgent issues for ensuring food security, accelerating economic development, and meeting the population's demand for quality food. The growing population, increasing demand for seafood, and limited capacity to supply agricultural products have made increasing the volume of fish caught a crucial direction.

However, in the matter of increasing the volume of fish caught, ensuring ecological stability and the rational use of natural resources are important factors. Overfishing can lead to a decline in fish populations, which in turn disrupts biological balance and harms the fishing industry in the long run. Therefore, it is necessary to introduce modern technologies, apply scientifically-

based fishing methods, and adhere to international ecological standards to effectively organize this process.

The Aidar-Arnasay Lakes System is a water body of ecological, economic, biological, and touristic importance in our country.[1] Due to the introduction of water from the Chordara reservoir into AAKT, many fish species from the local ichthyofauna have migrated, turning AAKT into a lake with the potential for industrial fishing. Since the Chordara reservoir was built during the planned economy period, programs for the formation of ichthyofauna and the development of fishing were implemented. A fish farming economy (hatchery) was established in the territory of Kazakhstan (Chordara), and the fish fingerlings grown there are transferred to the reservoir. As a result of such efforts, valuable fish species like pikeperch (*Sander lucioperca*) were introduced into the ichthyofauna, making the Chordara reservoir a significant fishing area[3].

Considering that AAKT is the largest water body with fishing significance in our country, it was decided in 2017 to transition to a special regime for industrial fishing, and thus the Aydar-Arnasoy State Unitary Enterprise was established (Resolution No. 124 of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan, dated 7.03.2017, "On organizational measures to ensure the effective use of the biological resources of the Aydar-Arnasoy Lakes System")[4].

Methodology

The research was conducted from 2019 to 2022 in three reservoirs of the Aidar-Arnasoy Lakes System: Tuzkon and Aidarkul Lakes, and Arnasoy Reservoir. The fishing studies were carried out in various locations of these reservoirs. To assess the economic efficiency of the research results, we can use two approaches:

Organizing fishing brigades: Establishing a network of fishermen by brigades in the water body and specializing them in catching large pikeperch will be necessary [Figure 1]. They should be equipped with gear of mesh sizes and larger. Nets should be placed in locations with more abundant perch and other small forage fish near the shore where pikeperch tend to "rest". That is, the nets should be set at some distance from the shore to areas where aquatic vegetation is concentrated.

Figure 1. Fish Species Caught by Fishing Brigades

Monitoring fishing near lake shores: The performance of fishing near lake shores by fishing brigades was monitored in various seasons (autumn, winter, spring). It should be noted that fish switch to active feeding in summer, and after the spawning season, their flesh quality is not as good, making them less desirable for commercial fishing during summer. The data obtained are presented in Table 1. After discussing with the head of the research brigade, we allocated one fisherman for catching pikeperch.

In 2021, the price of 1 kg of pikeperch was 35,000 UZS in January and March, and 34,000 UZS in September. Thus, the shore price (producer price) of pikeperch was determined to be 34,500 UZS.

Table 1.

Results of Monitoring Fishing Indicators of Fishermen's Brigades in the Aidar-Arnasoy Lakes System

N	Fish species	Total weight, kg	Price, UZS	Fuel consumption	Payment , UZS* 1-1 Boat= 2 people
23-24 January 2021 -y.					
1	Roach fish	266,7	2 667 000,00	300 liter	465 066,67
2	Common carp	159,2	7 164 000,00		
3	Pikeperch	154,4	5 404 000,00		
4	Crucian carp	25,85	517 000,00		
	Total	606,15	15 752 000,00	1 800 000 UZS	
20-21 September 2021 -y.					
1	Roach fish	262,3	2 623 000,00	300 liter	428 058,33
2	Common carp	143,45	6 455 250,00		
3	Pikeperch	141,3	4 945 500,00		
4	Crucian carp	30,9	618 000,00		
	Total	577,95	14 641 750,00	1800 000 UZS	
6-7 march 2021 -y.					
1	Roach fish	390,54	3 905 400,00	300 liter	902 403,33
2	Common carp	327,16	14 722 200,00		
3	Pikeperch	218,7	7 654 500,00		

4	Crucian carp	129,5	2 590 000,00		
	Total	1065,9	28 872 100,00	1 800 000 UZS	
*(information about the payment being 40% of the shore price)					

Fuel consumption for one boat in a conditional day in January. 12 boats consumed 300 liters of fuel in 5 days. The fuel cost at that time was 1.8 million UZS. Calculations show that one boat consumes 5 liters of gasoline per day. The daily cost of gasoline is therefore 30,000 UZS per day.

The average daily catch per boat was 10.1 kg/day in January, 9.6 kg/day in September, and 17.9 kg/day in March. When the data is consolidated, it results in an average of 12.5 kg/day. This figure is accepted for 9 months (since fishing is not conducted in summer, fishermen take a break). In terms of value, this means:

Payment to fishermen is 40% of the delivered fish. In January, daily payment was 93,000 UZS for 2 people; in September, 85,000 UZS for 2 people; and in March, 180,000 UZS for 2 people, with an average of 119,000 UZS for 2 people. Taking into account the provided details, we allocate one fisherman (with an assistant) for one boat on a conditional basis. This fisherman uses fuel (gasoline) for their boat, owns 30 nets (the annual cost of using the nets (depreciation) is 600,000 UZS). The other fishermen continue their daily work, catching other types of fish without our recommendations. Thus, one boat (fisherman and assistant) will have the following production cost per day:

However, some adjustments are necessary: in summer, the fish meat does not meet quality standards, so fishermen do not fish. In such cases, the profitability rate of fishing is 52%. See Table 2.

Table 2.

Economic Efficiency of Research Results (Cost of One Boat's Daily Work. Boat/day)

N	Indicators	UZS	January	September	March	August	Difference	Mean
1	Labor payment	thousand UZS	93	85	180	75	105	119
2	Fuel consumption	thousand UZS	30	30	30	30	0	30
3	Net depreciation	thousand UZS	5	5	5	5	0	5
4	Administrative expenses	thousand UZS	38	38	38	38	0	38
5	Other expenses	thousand UZS	38	38	38	38	0	38

6	Tax	thousand UZS	23	20	43,6	16	27, 6	27
7	Total expenses	thousand UZS	227	216	334,6	202	132,6	257
8	Total weight of caught fish	Kg	10,9	10,4	17,9	9,1	9	12,5
9	Price of caught fish	thousand UZS	381,5	353, 6	626,5	309	317,5	438
10	Weight share of caught fish	% (percent)	25%	24%	20%	21%	5%	22,5%
11	Price share of caught fish	% (percent)	34%	33%	27%	30%	7%	31%
12	Total income	thousand UZS	177, 5	157, 6	335,5	123	212,5	208
13	Net income	thousand UZS	154, 5	137, 6	291,9	107	184,9	181
14	Profitability rate	% (percent)	68%	63,%	87%	52%	35%	70%

Conclusion. Thus, the profitability of fishing by the crew of the boat allocated for catching white sla is 70%. It can be seen that the share of white sla among the fish caught in September was 24% by weight and 33% by price; in January - 25% by weight and 34% by price; in March - 27% by weight and 20% by price. Thus, white sla is a fish of significant fishing value among the fish caught in almost all seasons.

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